

NEOVASCULOSTOP

PARADIGM SHIFT IN NEOVASCULARIZATION TREATMENT

Acronym:
NeoVasculoStop

Project Title:
Natural Intraocular Photoactivation of Compounds to Fight Retinopathies

Grant Agreement No:
101047120

Call:
HORIZON-EIC-2021-PATHFINDEROPEN-01

Deliverable	Data management plan D1.4
Associated WP	WP1
Associated Task(s)	Task 1.6
Due Date	31.08.2022
Date Delivered	30.08.2022
Prepared by	Dr. Peter Ruzicska (LC)
Partners involved	All
Authors	Dr. Peter Ruzicska
Deliverable Version	Version 1
Dissemination Level	PU - Public

List of abbreviation

Abbrevia- tion	Definition
CSV	Comma Separated Values file
CTA	Clinical trial application
DMP	Data management plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
FAIR	Findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability
OA	Open Access
OAI-PMH	Open Archive Initiative - Protocol for Metadata Harvesting

Contents

1. Data summary	1
2. Fair data	1
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata.....	1
2.2. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses).....	2
3. Allocation of resources	2
4. Data Description	3

1. Data summary

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for the NeoVasculoStop project is developed to facilitate data flow and utilization of the data between the parties, including third parties/public where appropriate, and ensure proper data preservation for future use. DMP is developed in line with Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon Europe projects. The purpose of the DMP is to cover the complete research data life cycle and to describe the types of data that will be generated/collected during the project, the standards that will be used, how data will be preserved and what parts will be shared for verification or use. The team is aware of the sensitivity of research data related data protection, as well as exploitation and licensing needs, so it will keep certain data closed and stick with "as open as possible, as closed as necessary"

Mostly research data will be collected during the project.

2. Fair data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Data Findable: All data designated for Open Access to research data, will be named according to a specific file naming convention including a versioning system. Dataset description will be done by an added .txt-File that describes the data by a text, so that a potential re-user gets context and can evaluate the data. Additionally, the metadata will be documented in a .txt-File "Metadata". The Metadata file is produced by the author of the document. Relevant additional metadata will be entered as well. By the time of publication, the data(sets) will get an DOI as unique identifier. They will be indexed by a searchable resource by its publication. The producer, handler and storage of these data is described according to the relevant work packages and tasks in Chapter 4. "Data description". This is a living document so it will be updated each time a new document is created.

Data Openly Accessible: In line with the Open Access principle, the consortium partners will follow two main routes in NeoVasculoStop:

1. Self-archiving: The partners have identified the following acceptable choices for self-archiving:

- *Subject-based repositories:* arXiv.org, ResearchGate.

- *Centralized repositories:* NeoVasculoStop related publications can be made available on own company/institutional websites and/or on the project website and on Open access websites. To determine what repository to choose, entering the Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE) has been recommended (www.openaire.eu), where the National Open Access Desks provides further assistance. Besides the published article, the overlaying data necessary to validate the results will also be deposited in a data repository.

2. Open access publishing: In the frame of Horizon Europe program, Open Access, as a step towards Open Science, is obligatory. Concurrently, in line with the Horizon Europe rules, open access will be granted to all scientific publications resulting from the project. Broader access to scientific publications helps to: build on previous research results, encourage collaboration among researchers and avoid duplication of effort and resources, speed up innovation and further involve citizens and society (improved transparency of the scientific process). To this end, the partners will pay special attention to publishing in Open Access journals, while also caring to maintain the copyrights of their work. Moreover, it should be underlined that the NeoVasculoStop website will provide OA to all public documents, public deliverable reports and produced dissemination/communication materials.

Data Interoperable: The project partners in accordance with the EU regulations make sure that the research data produced in the project and described in Chapter 4. will be interoperable.

Therefore, data repositories (places where data produced during the project is stored) will be based on the DataCite-standard. The meta data produced by the owner of the data will contain minimum the following fields: Subject, Licence, Description.

It will also be possible to reference the linked resources via an identifier. Common interfaces like OAI-PMH will be contained, for allowing the exchange and harvesting of metadata into other data collections and into the repository of the EU “OpenAIRE”. The data created in this project will be made available in standardized, wide-spread formats.

Data Reusable: The project data will remain reusable by delivering them in standardized, wide-spread data formats (for example: docx, pdf, xls, xlsx, mp3, etc.). There is no embargo foreseen. The data will be released with a clear and accessible data usage license (Open Definition license) which will allow the further processing under attribution and sharing under the same conditions. For each item, a single master data file will be created. A project member will be assigned to be responsible for that master file. All changes to master files will be recorded. Copies of the master files will be stored in regular intervals. The quality of data will be assured.

2.2. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)

Data relevant for commercial use will be exploited through patenting, and potentially licensing. In terms of further use for research purposes, the data will be used to further plan and design later phases of clinical development and explore the therapeutic utilization in the context of other human pathological conditions and ultimately apply the generated knowledge in the clinical practice for the benefit of patients and healthcare systems.

3. Allocation of resources

All partners are requested to collect and manage the data in accordance with the DMP and other common professional practices, especially the task leaders. The WP leaders will be responsible for the implementation of the DMP and will monitor data management activities.

4. Data Description

The list of WPs is presented in Table 1 and Data management is included in all of them.

Table I.

WP	Lead beneficiary
WP1	LC
WP2	VICHEM
WP3	SE
WP4	SE
WP5	EXPERIM
WP6	NEOX
WP7	EXPERIM
WP8	EXPERIM

Data summary of WP1
Task 1.1 General project management (Leader: LC, partners involved: All; M1-48)
What is the purpose of the data collection / generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data related to project management will be created and stored.
What types and formats of data will the project generate / collect?
Emails, Teams documents, word documents will be generated and stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile (Citrix Systems) hosted by the coordinator (Experimentica Oy).
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 4 GB.
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.

Task 1.2 Communication and dissemination (Leader: LC, partners involved: All; M1-48)
What is the purpose of the data collection / generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Project communication and dissemination data will be created in this task.
What types and formats of data will the project generate / collect?
Word documents, PDFs, pictures, and videos.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The expected size is 10 GB
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
To the scientific community and the general public. Data will be accessible to the scientific community upon the open access principles. Before the data go public, they will undergo necessary process of validation and inspection and only then they will be released to the scientific community.
Task 1.3 Knowledge management (Leader: LC, partners involved: All; M1-48)
What is the purpose of the data collection / generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data will be collected in relation to knowledge management.
What types and formats of data will the project generate / collect?
Emails, Teams documents, word documents will be generated and stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile (Citrix Systems) hosted by the coordinator (Experimentica Oy).
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The expected size is 2 GB

To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
To the project partners and the IP manager
Task 1.4 Exploitation (Leader: LC, partners involved: All; M1-48)
What is the purpose of the data collection / generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Exploitation intentions and other related data will be collected from partners. This will be collated into Key Exploitable Results table. This will be a living document.
What types and formats of data will the project generate / collect?
Emails, Teams documents, word documents will be generated and stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile (Citrix Systems) hosted by the coordinator (Experimentica Oy).
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The expected size is 8 GB
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
To the project partners, he exploitation expert and EU officials
Task 1.5 Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) (Leader: LC, partners involved: All; M1-48)
What is the purpose of the data collection / generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
During the project Responsible Research and Innovation seminars will be held. In relation to this surveys and interviews will be carried out. The data will be anonymized where applicable.
What types and formats of data will the project generate / collect?
Emails, Teams documents, word documents will be generated and stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile (Citrix Systems) hosted by the coordinator (Experimentica Oy).
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.

What is the expected size of the data?
The expected size is 8 GB
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
To the project partners, the RRI expert and EU officials.
Task 1.6 Data management (Leader: LC, partners involved: All; M1-48)
What is the purpose of the data collection / generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data will be collected to prepare and update the DMP of the project. DMP will be prepared. This will be a living document. LC will be responsible for the maintenance of this document.
What types and formats of data will the project generate / collect?
Emails, Teams documents, word documents will be generated and stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile (Citrix Systems) hosted by the coordinator (Experimentica Oy).
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The expected size is 5 GB
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
To the project partners, the data management expert and EU officials

Data summary of WP2
Tasks 2.1 – 2.6
What is the purpose of the data collection / generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
During the project mostly experimental data will be collected. This will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
What types and formats of data will the project generate / collect?
Experiments documented in written form will be stored and archived in Vichem office headquarter. Measurement readouts, generated in digital forms, word documents will be generated and stored on the server of Vichem in Hungary.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The expected size is 12 GB
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
To the scientific community, project partners, and EU officials
Task 2.7
What is the purpose of the data collection / generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
During the patent preparation IP databases search will be carried out and patent documents created mostly from the experimental results. During the preparation phase this will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by Vichem.
What pes and formats of data will the project generate / collect?
Mostly word documents will be created.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.

What is the expected size of the data?
The expected size is 2 GB
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
To the scientific community, and IP officials.

Data summary of WP3
Tasks 3.1 – 3.4
What is the purpose of the data collection / generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
During the project mostly experimental data will be collected. This will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
What types and formats of data will the project generate / collect?
Experiments documented in written form will be stored and archived in SE office headquarter. Measurement readouts, generated in digital forms, word, excel documents will be generated and stored on the server of SE in Hungary and cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile (Citrix Systems) hosted by the coordinator (Experimentica Oy). External databases (PyRAT, Scionics Computer Innovation GmbH, Dresden, Germany; Animal Data base) use their own servers.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The expected size is 12 GB
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
To the scientific community, project partners, and EU officials

Data summary of WP4
Tasks 4.1 – 4.5
What is the purpose of the data collection / generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
During the project mostly experimental data will be collected. This will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
What types and formats of data will the project generate / collect?
Experiments documented in written form will be stored and archived in SE office headquarter. Measurement readouts, generated in digital forms, word, excel documents will be generated and stored on the server of SE in Hungary. Experiments documented in written form will be archived at Experimentica (EXPERIM) in Finland and EXPERIM_UAB in Lithuania. Measurement readouts, generated in digital forms, word, excel documents will be generated and stored in cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile (Citrix Systems) hosted by the coordinator (Experimentica Oy). External databases (PyRAT, Scionics Computer Innovation GmbH, Dresden, Germany; Animal Data base) use their own servers.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The expected size is 12 GB
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
To the scientific community, project partners, and EU officials

Data summary of WP5
Tasks 5.1 – 5.3
What is the purpose of the data collection / generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
During the project mostly experimental data will be collected. This will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
What types and formats of data will the project generate / collect?
Experiments documented in written form will be stored and archived. Measurement readouts, generated in digital forms, word documents will be generated and stored in SE server in Hungary. Experiments documented in written form will be stored and archived at Experimentica (EXPERIM_UAB) in Lithuania and in cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile (Citrix Systems) hosted by the coordinator (Experimentica Oy). The results and report from subcontracted GLP toxicity testing will be stored in cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile (Citrix Systems) hosted by the coordinator (Experimentica Oy).
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The expected size is 12 GB
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
To the scientific community, project partners, and EU officials

Data summary of WP6
Tasks 6.1 – 6.3
What is the purpose of the data collection / generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data in relation to the preparation of the phase I. clinical trial document will be collected in this task.
What types and formats of data will the project generate / collect?
The clinical trial document will be prepared and stored on NEOX server and the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile (Citrix Systems) hosted by the coordinator (Experimentica Oy).
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The expected size is 2 GB
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
To the scientific community, project partners, and EU officials

Data summary of WP7
Ethics requirements
What is the purpose of the data collection / generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
The objective is to ensure compliance with the 'ethics requirements' therefore documents related to this task will be created in this work package.
What types and formats of data will the project generate / collect?
Documents will be created and distributed to project partners through the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile (Citrix Systems) hosted by the coordinator (Experimentica Oy).
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.

What is the expected size of the data?
The expected size is 2 GB
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
To the scientific community, project partners, and EU officials

Data summary of WP8
Coordination
What is the purpose of the data collection / generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
The data created during project coordination in form of emails, word documents, excel sheets etc. will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project coordinator.
What types and formats of data will the project generate / collect?
Technical/scientific review meeting documents for RP1, RP2 and RP3. The generated documents will be stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile (Citrix Systems) hosted by the coordinator (Experimentica Oy).
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The expected size is 2 GB
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Project partners, and EU officials

